

PSYCHOTHERAPY OF NEUROSIS IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS.

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Annotation. The article covers the problems of neurosis in children and adolescents, family influence and environment of the world and a number of components on the development of personality. In addition, devoted to psychological features of age period of children and adolescents, offered some practical recommendations of prophylactic character.

Key words: children, adolescents, neurosis, psychological features, image "I", age period, emotional relations.

More than 60 percent of the population of our country are young people. Sh.M.Mirziyoev, the honorable president of our country, has been paying special attention to youth policy.

It is no secret to anyone that the future of our country is in the hands of a healthy generation if we pay attention to the meaning of the proverb "Healthy body - healthy mind". 2023 has been declared as the "year of attention to people and quality education", and the state program for this year has been developed. At the core of this program, the strategic directions of the healthy lifestyle of the people and the future of the healthy generation were defined. One of the main tasks of the state program was to pay particular attention to family issues. We all know that the psychological literacy of the citizens of Uzbekistan plays an important role in the development of children in the family, education and upbringing in the school.

Mental development of students is an age that is distinguished by its special characteristics during childhood and adolescence. Especially in adolescence, a very important component of self-awareness is formed - responsibility for one's behavior and feeling that only one is the cause of its outcome. That is, for a teenager, not only other people, but also his own feelings and experiences become the object of observation. His "self-concept" appears as a motivating force for active action for his future.

The name of our scientific research work "Ibrat" as a socio-psychological phenomenon was analyzed in the monograph on the role of adolescents in the socialization of adolescents, focusing our attention on the psychological analysis of adolescent students. In the work of the monograph, such age-related situations were identified in the self-development of teenage students. In particular, it was analyzed that self-awareness plays an important role in adolescents and children.

Self-awareness is discovering one's inner world, having a holistic idea about it, evaluating one's emotional attitude, mental, moral and volitional qualities (self-evaluation). The component embedded in the process of self-realization is a factor that directs, strengthens, corrects, that is, determines the nature of its flow. The fact that adolescence is a

difficult and complicated period is connected with many psychological, physiological and social factors. During this period, serious changes occur in the life of a teenager, in his psyche, in the physiological conditions of his body, and in his social status.

This period roughly corresponds to the time when the child studies in grades 5-9 and is between the ages of 11-12 and 14-15 years, and it is desirable to know that the changes in the character traits of these age periods are carried out on the basis of psychological laws. Also, in my textbook "Age Psychology" published by my authorship, extensive information is given about the psychological characteristics of young people and the features of development and formation in cognitive processes. Adolescent students have:

At the age of 10, a child quickly perceives a balanced life, is trusting, obedient to his parents, and does not care about his appearance, so this is considered a "golden age".

The 11-year-old organism is undergoing restructuring, children are unnatural, show negativity, change their mood quickly, and express dissatisfaction with their parents.

The 12-year-old has a quick temper, a positive attitude towards the world is formed, autonomy in relation to the family and influence on peers increases in the teenager. Intelligence, sense of humor, endurance, initiative, appearance and attitude towards members of the opposite sex begin to increase.

The 13-year-old is characterized by attention to his inner world, introversion, he is sensitive to self-criticism and criticism, critical of his parents, chooses friends, excitement and excitement increase.

In 14-year-old teenagers, introversion changes to extroversion, they become energetic, sociable, self-confident, more attentive to others, and begin to recognize poverty among them.

15-year-olds become more independent, which leads them to stress with family and school. They have an increased desire to move with the group and fit in with the group.

16-year-olds are considered to be teenagers, and their balance, enjoyment of life, inner independence, emotional stability, tendency to deal, and desire for the future increase.

The purpose of commenting on the characteristic aspects of age periods above is that the psychological description of age characteristics provides an opportunity to analyze and evaluate changes in children's behavior.

In these young people, negative conditions are observed in the psychological conditions of children and adolescents. The occurrence of negative situations causes a psychological change in the child, i.e. neurosis.

Невроз означает (от греческого слова «нейрон» — нерв), в традиционном понимании наблюдаются состояния нервного расстройства, эмоционального возбуждения, проблемы с самоконтролем. То есть в результате такой ситуации у детей проявляются проблемные признаки:

- not mastering the sciences;
- lagging behind in intellectual development;
- engage more in other types of activities (mobile phone, internet networks);
- loss of interest in basic subjects;
- failure to fulfill public tasks;
- neglect of material possessions in the classroom;
- rudeness, skipping classes;
- dirtiness in classes;
- violation of public order;

- unreasonable behavior
- indifference to educational activities, etc.

In our life, we encounter a situation limited to one of the common concepts in pedagogical activity, children or teenagers with deviant behavior, difficult to educate. However, when we analyze the real situation, it is possible to observe symptoms of neurosis in children and adolescents. For example, medically, chronic diseases of internal organs, problems with hearing, vision, speech, memory, attention.

Socially - living in an unacceptable family, living in a low-income family, situations of discrimination or regular bullying, refugees or immigrants, adjustment problems related to transferring to another school, class, etc.

According to psychological sources, types of neurosis are divided into types for various reasons. Clinical neuroses (manifests symptoms of illness), neuroticism (lack of emotional self-control, pessimism), negativism (problems in controlling behavior, changes in behavior, conflicting behavior in relation to relationships), studying neurolinguistics (changes in the brain mechanisms of speech activity) are concepts.

The main reason for the emergence of neurosis is the increase in the feeling of unhappiness, unfulfillment of needs, dissatisfaction with living conditions, failure to fulfill goals and dreams, and factors that lead to neurotic disputes and conflicts appear.

According to psychoanalytic information about neuroses, our scientists have studied the effects of Oedipus complex, fear and defense mechanisms in explaining the nature of neuroses.

The effect of fear on the emergence of neurosis has been observed, and fear has the same nature in all people. It takes us completely at lightning speed, does not allow a person to control such a spontaneous attack. We are powerless in the face of fear, we succumb to it. Panic occurs when fear is completely out of control. Here we fall into a state of helpless childish fear that has supposedly already been overcome.

But at the same time, fear can be a signal (sign) of perceived and goal-directed danger. We perceive it and process it with the power of our psychic abilities and are able to face the fear and eliminate the danger behind it.

Uncontrollable, automatic panic-like fear is reminiscent of the first, archaic stage of personality development. The ability to signal fear, on the contrary, indicates a certain level of maturity of the individual. At the same time, when automatic fear is able to crush and destroy the "I", alarm fear serves the "I", warning it of danger.

Such protection against danger should consist of the ability to face it realistically.

But such ability is not yet formed in childhood. Therefore, it is natural that children's fears are common, which we do not know from our own personal memories or from observing our children: fear of the dark, fear of loneliness, fear of wrinkles, fear of lightning.

Out of necessity, the child discovers psychic mechanisms that protect him from fear. The fear is reduced to a somewhat tolerable level. "I" builds a kind of wall for its own protection, which separates it from danger, behind which it can hide when necessary. For this, the protective wall must be strong enough to contain fear. And danger does not always come from outside, it can also break through the inner personal psychic shell. Therefore, it is necessary to know the gap between the protective wall that prevents external and internal danger.

Initially, psychoanalysis looked for the cause of neurotic states in external trauma. Later, this theory was replaced by the theory of tendencies, that is, internal, sexual and aggressive tendencies were studied as the cause of mental disorders. The protective wall or defense mechanism, in other words, suppression, is an active action of the self, as a result of which tendencies that have risen from the subconscious to the consciousness are suppressed, like objects that rise to the surface of water and sink again. Why is it submerged? Moving from physics to psychology, the answer can be answered: if the water rises to the surface, fear will reawaken.

What protective forms of fear can be distinguished?

Fear of Punishment, Fear of Injury, Fear of Imaginary Castration, Fear of Embarrassment, Fear of Losing the Willingness to Be a Significant Participant in the Relationship, Serious Consequences, Fear Characteristic of Disorders, Fear of Losing Someone Valued by This Person, Serious Consequences, Disorders A characteristic fear is the fear of losing someone dear to him.

These are all types of fear that cause neurotic disorders. What keeps the pod underwater? Affective excitement, guilt and shame in equal measure. So, we can observe complex unconscious processes in children and adolescents. The inclination tends to rise up like a pod, which evokes feelings of fear, shame, or guilt. Therefore, it is necessary to protect not only from fear, but also from feelings of guilt and shame.

Defense mechanisms to trigger a defense reaction can include: The "I" who is crushed (figuratively speaking, dirtied) under the demands of "He", fearing punishment, prevents the fulfillment of these demands with all his might, and a "reaction" in the form of an anti-reaction of the "I" is formed. This means that the "I" reacts strongly against contamination by garbage and becomes a fanatical lover of cleanliness. For this, it is recommended to use an isolation protection mechanism.

Imagination or fantasies related to desire are isolated (separated) from affect (the general meaning of affect is used together with emotion, emotionality, feeling, mood, the modern meaning is a general and long-lasting intense emotional "passion" state). This affect can also be a direct affect of fear. For example, a teenager is angry with a friend and wants to insult him. In order to preserve his friendship, he must isolate his anger from the idea of a "friend". The neurotic achievement in this is that the affect of anger is removed from the concept of friend. As a result, anger is much safer than anger associated with the concept of a friend.

The defense mechanism of confusion is that the fear does not appear in the primary situation that provoked it, for example, in front of a father who treats the child harshly, but somewhat later, for example, in front of a dog that threatens the child, it appears in relation to the dog. This defense mechanism is more manifested in phobias, it achieves that fear does not appear in front of a strict father, if the child does not encounter a dog, he is completely free from fear.

Projection is a defense mechanism - image displacement - here, the fear is directed to another object. This mechanism consists in the fact that, in order to protect ourselves from unpleasant instinctive tendencies, we simply project them onto other people, push them away from us. In this, we perceive the person we are projecting our inclinations not as they really are, but in accordance with our imagination.

Recommendations for the prevention of neurosis:

Implementation of goal-oriented educational work with children from their early age;
study their interests and wishes;

healthy family relations, failure to solve economic and various problems in the family
with the participation of children and adolescents;

spending time to strengthen strict control and attention over the actions of children
and adolescents;

application of punitive measures in relation to the act performed, in the event that no
bodily injury was caused;

Timely fulfillment of the functional tasks of parents:

communicative, facilitative, relaxing, reproductive, etc.;

increasing children's interest in reading in the family, conducting interviews;

formation of psychological intimacy with children and teenagers.

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